

Coherent & Cross-compliant Ocean Governance for Delivering the EU Green Deal for European Seas

Case Study: French Mediterranean case study

STEP 2

Step 2 – Assessing the state of play and challenges in coherence and cross-compliance

Research question addressed:

- Does the interplay between River Basin management (WFD), marine spatial plans, and MSFD strategies provide a coherent approach to govern the marine environment?
- How does the current performance of the marine framework's delivery mechanisms influence the achievement of their intended objectives?
- How do the implementation mechanisms related to sectoral issues (energy, fisheries) influence the realization of both marine policies and the Green Deal objective?
- What can be learnt from impediments and best practices to facilitate the internalization of the key GD objectives into sectoral policies?

Policies being assessed: MSFD, MSPD, WFD, Fisheries policy, offshore wind policy

Guidances on the text reading:

Abbreviation explanations: to keep consistency with deliverables published in the past 6 months on the French Mediterranean governance (e.g. Regina MSP deliverable 3.1), I decided to keep the same abbreviations which are in French (e.g. SDAGE should be translated as RBMP but stays as SDAGE in the text).

To make it clearer, the following color code has been adopted: **green** for land-related documents, **dark blue** for sea related documents, **clear blue** for inland-water documents.

Box 1: Brief description of marine environment policies in France

The French Mediterranean coastline represents a critical hotspot of biodiversity, characterized by the presence of over ten protected species, including *Posidonia oceanica* seagrass meadows, as well as ecologically valuable landscapes such as rocky inlets and islands. However, this marine region is strongly subjected to human pressures. These include intensive maritime activities (e.g., cruise shipping, commercial navigation, recreational tourism, and fishing), freshwater-borne pollution (particularly plastic waste discharged by the Rhône River), and land-based impacts (such as urbanization and untreated or insufficiently treated wastewater discharges).¹

In France, the WFD was transposed in 2004¹ and orientates the entire water policy towards results objectives among which the good status of waters. The WFD is operationalised through River Basin Management Plans (RBMPs), which define ambitious targets for the conservation and restoration of aquatic ecosystems. These plans apply to river basins as well as to coastal waters extending up to one nautical mile from the shoreline baseline.

France adopts a centralized approach to marine environmental governance. Strategic frameworks developed under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD) are designed and elaborated at the national level. However, their implementation is delegated to the maritime façade level. To enhance both marine biodiversity protection and the coherence of maritime economic development, France has adopted a unified spatial management framework: the Document Stratégique de Façade (DSF). This integrative document consolidates the objectives and measures of both the MSFD and MSPD, facilitating a more balanced approach to environmental and economic priorities in marine spatial planning.

Historically, the marine environment was partially addressed within the scope of the RBMPs, particularly concerning chemical contamination and eutrophication. Following the implementation of the MSFD and MSPD, responsibility for these issues was retained within the RBMP framework. This strategic choice reinforced land-sea continuity and promoted alignment of environmental objectives across freshwater and marine domains.

From a legal standpoint, both RBMPs and marine strategies are overarching frameworks. All other planning instruments—including terrestrial and sectoral development plans—are required to conform to the objectives and measures outlined therein. Nevertheless, the practical realization of this legal coherence remains limited. This is largely due to the multiplicity of planning documents and the competing economic and employment-oriented goals they pursue, compounded by insufficient human and financial resources to ensure effective cross-sectoral integration and alignment.

On paper, marine environment management policies objectives are the same throughout France. The French global strategy and objectives is gathered through France's national strategy for the sea and coastline (SNML). However, there are some regional declinations to better adapt to the regional marine ecosystems, watersheds, and economic stakes.

The main marine related policies are drafted as follow:

- The **MSFD and MSPD** are adapted at the Maritime façade level through the Façade Strategic Document (**DSF**) but drafted mostly at the national level.
- The **WFD** is transposed at the Hydrographic basin level through the **RBMP**

To this two documents, other policies and planning documents have an impact on the marine environment

- The land-related document (**SRADDET**) which allow coastal municipalities to develop a sea development schemes (SMVM). This **SMVM** has a strategic importance because it is anterior to the MSPD (early 2000's). this overlap explains why the MSPD is included in the same strategic document than the MSFD
- The biodiversity protection document such as the **Habitat and Bird directives**
- The local planning documents such as the **MPA management plans**, the local declination of SDAGE called SAGE and the SMVM
- The **marine energy policy framework** built in the recent past year to develop the sector
- The **fisheries policy framework**, that supports the implementation of the Common Fisheries policies and includes the **EMFAF** program.

Figure 1 Policies and plans involved in the management of sea in France (modified from Abregal, C. (2021) INRAE)

	Planification and biodiversity	Energy legislation	Impacts on offshore wind planning
2009	Grenelle 1 st programming law relating to the implementation of the Grenelle Environment (climate change)		→ Reduction x4 CO2 emissions by 2050
2015		Law on energy transition for green growth	→ Encourages OW sector development
2018	1st Document Stratégique de Façade (MaS)		→ Only 3 strategic objectives on OW development
2019		Law on energy and climate	→ Objective to reduce nuclear part in energy consumption at 50% by 2035 => OW is an alternative
2020		Multiannual energy programming	→ Establishes the operational framework for OW planning with an objective of 2.4 to 3 GW by 2023 and 5.2 to 6.2 GW by 2028
2021	MaS Program of Measuras		→ Only 3/81 actions related to OW development
2022			
2023		Law on Renewable Energy Acceleration	→ Simplifies administrative procedures for OW projects and introduces mechanisms of local public consultations
2024	2nd Document Stratégique de Façade (MaS) debate including offshore wind		→ OW planning represented 1/2 of the issues covered in the MaS national public debate

Figure 2 marine and energy legislation impacting offshore wind planning in France (source: Laura Bastide (2025). Balancing offshore wind energy ambitions and marine biodiversity protection, an example of marine spatial planning in the Provence-Alpes-Côte-d'Azur region, CrossGov)

Figure 3 Fisheries and biodiversity regulations and plans (source: Laura Bastide (2025). Can fisheries policy implementation mechanisms be aligned with EU biodiversity objectives?, Crossgov)

Box 2: brief overview of competencies repartition in the French Mediterranean sea

One of the main variables to consider when looking at the sea management in France is that the sea is a “matter of the state” (quoted in many interviews) and many decisions are still centralised. However, a key role is given to the regional level (NUTS 2) in the implementation of national marine strategies and priorities.

The Façade Strategic Document (implementing the Marine Strategy (Mas)) orientation are decided at a national level. It is then declined at the regional scale to facilitate its implementation. However, frustrations emerge as local actors consider it does not sufficiently take into account the regional specificities and can lead to a diminished consideration of regional challenges (interviews).

Management of the marine environment, particularly in the part of the Public Maritime Domain that extends from the coastline to 12 nautical miles, involves a wide variety of players at regional level. These include the **Maritime Prefect**, who represents the State's authority at sea (mostly responsible for decision taken after 12 nm), State regional departments such as the **Interregional Directorate for the Sea (DIRM)** coordinating the Façade Strategic Document) with support of the Regional Department for the Environment, Planning and Housing (**DREAL**) who plays an important role in the land-sea interface, as well as the **Regional Administration** (implementing **EMFAF**), and State operators such as the Water Agency Rhône-Méditerranée-Corse (**AERMC** implementing the RBMP and managing most of the Façade Strategic Document funding) and the French Biodiversity Office (**OFB**) (managing the MPA strategies as well as most of the biodiversity protection projects). For sectoral policies, there are also committees such as those for fisheries (**FranceAgrimer** and **CNDPME**) or specialised commissions for offshore wind farms (**France Energie Marine, RTE**). Finally, many private players and NGO-type associations are involved (France Nature environment (**FNE**) and the World Wild Fund-Mediterranean (**WWF**) among others for the French Mediterranean sea).

Institutions responsible for implementing European marine directives in France

Figure 4 Institutions responsible for implementation marine framework (European and national) in France (Source: Laura Bastide, 2024)

Coherence attribute nr. 1: Policy Objective	
The outcomes, impacts, or the results that the policy sets out to achieve, as specified in the articles of the policy document, as well as broader objectives referred to in the preamble. May be referred to in policy documents as goals, objectives, targets, or commitments.	For policies to be coherent: - The policy objectives should be aligned or complementary and not contradict or impede each other.

1. Is the policy cross-referencing the policy objectives of another policy?

As indicated in the table above, many policies at play in the French Mediterranean are intertwined. To make reading easier for the authors of the CrossGov 3.2 and 3.3 reports, I separated for this section the analysis related to 3.2 and 3.3.

Task 3.2: (this section includes Facade Strategic Document (DSF), River Basin Management Plan (RBMP), Sea enhancement Scheme (SRADET/SMVM))

To understand the alignment of the policies and objectives, an element to take into account is the **multiplicity** of planning documents and their **level of implementation** (see Box 1) and the **institutions** implementing them (See Box 2).

Historically, the marine environment was partially addressed within the scope of the RBMPs, particularly concerning chemical contamination and eutrophication. Following the implementation of the MSFD and MSPD, responsibility for these issues was retained within the RBMP framework. This strategic choice reinforced land-sea continuity and promoted alignment of environmental objectives across freshwater and marine domains.

From a legal standpoint, both RBMPs and marine strategies are overarching frameworks. All other planning instruments—including terrestrial and sectoral development plans—are required to conform to the objectives and measures outlined therein. Nevertheless, the practical realization of this legal coherence remains limited. This is largely due to the multiplicity of planning documents and the competing economic and employment-oriented goals they pursue, compounded by insufficient human and financial resources to ensure effective cross-sectoral integration and alignment.

WFD and MSFD have the same objective: reaching at good status of fresh (quantitative and qualitative) and marine waters. Related planning document in France aims at achieving these objectives. Both the WFD and MSFD overlap in part (1nm/coastal/transitional waters), but it can be considered that MSFD is extending the reach of WFD (RBMP to the entirety of the country's territorial waters. Going even beyond, France has an interesting approach: the MSPD and the MSFD are both operationalised in the same document, the **Façade Strategic Document (MSFD/MSPD)**. Having both policies in the same document can support good coherence between both directives. Besides, the Façade Strategic Document (MSFD/ MSPD) must be compatible with the **River Basin Management Plan (RBMP)**. In each of the planning documents, there is a section (often short 1-2 pages) which explains why and how both documents are compatible. However, there are no operational details on how this coherence is concretely implemented.

In their Program of measures (POM), the **RBMP** and **DSF** explicitly indicate which measures supports the other document's measures.

<p>6 Example from the SDAGE POM on how it supports DSF measures</p>	
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Another key component to consider is the source-to-sea continuum. Land-related documents [Regional plan for spatial planning, sustainable development and territorial equality \(SRADDET\)](#) from the Provence-Alpes-Côte-d'Azur Region (**PACA**) are on paper compatible with the DSF and RBMP. However, they have different objectives with a strong emphasis on economic development for the SRADDET and very few mentions of biodiversity protection, climate change or Zero pollution. This can be explained also be explained by the time this land planning document was drafted (2018). It has no cross-references to the [DSF](#) and very few on the [RBMP](#) either.

Task 3.3: Energy and fishery policy coherence with MSFD, MSPD and WFD

Energy strategies and fisheries funding orientations (not policy) are framed at a national level in France. The objectives are different from the marine framework strategies. The fisheries policies aim at preserving employment and economy and the offshore wind policies aim at developing this new sector and ensuring energetic independence.

The Region manages the EMFAF funding and the [Interregional Directorate for the Mediterranean Sea \(DIRM\)](#) and [Maritime Prefecture \(PREMAR\)](#) manage the implementation of offshore wind energy farms.

To facilitate the coordination and uses of the sea. The [Façade Strategic Document \(MSFD/MSPD\)](#) includes “vocation area maps” where biodiversity issues and activities such as fisheries and offshore wind are displayed on a same map. The aim of these maps is to bring together the objectives and measures relating to these different policies.

Besides, there are indicators linking environmental stakes and economic pressures in Annex “objectives indicators” from the DSF.

7 2019 DSF strategic plan shows 30 vocation area in the Mediterranean Sea

2. Are the policy objectives aligned between policies? (substance as well as spatial and temporal scales such as deadlines for achievement, and geographical application)

To make reading easier for the authors of the CrossGov 3.2 and 3.3 reports, I separated for this section the analysis related to 3.2 and 3.3.

Task 3.2: (this section includes DSF, SDAGE, SRADDET/SMVM)

Substance:

Overall, the [DSF](#) and the [RBMP](#) aim at achieving common objectives such as Good Environmental Status including biodiversity protection and Zero pollution. It is mandatory for both documents to be coherent through their objectives and program of measures. The [RBMP](#) has four general objectives: good environmental status for surface and groundwater bodies, non-degradation, pollution reduction and the specific objectives for protected areas. The [DSF](#) has four objectives, two related to the environment: protection of marine habitats and species and pressure reduction, and two related to

the economy with the development of a sustainable blue economy and the ambition of France having influence as a maritime nation.

The **Regional plan for spatial planning, sustainable development and territorial equality (SRADDET)** lists its 10 objectives as follows: two objectives on territorial equity, two on infrastructure development and spatial management, 1 on climate change, 1 on air pollution, 1 on energy management, 1 on combating climate change, 1 on biodiversity protection and 1 on waste prevention. Reading the denomination, these objectives are aligned with the Green Deal and marine policies objectives, nevertheless, there is no mention of marine ecosystems in the chapter dedicated to the sea-coast development plan, only elements on economic development. This economic development is not led with a blue sustainable economy strategy what leads to contradictor objectives.

Spatial and temporal scale:

	SDAGE		DSF (and PAMM)	SRADDET
Institution	SDAGE cycles	Water Agency cycles	DIRM	PACA regional council
Adoption of 1 st plan	2010–2015	2013–2018	2012–2018	2020
Adoption 2 nd plan	2016–2021	2019–2024	2018–2024	
Adoption 3 rd plan	2022–2027	2024–2029	2024–2030	

There is no alignment between spatial and temporal scales, which has been underlined as a source of inconsistency (interviews). Temporal scale can have a strong influence on the marine-related planning coherence. We can notice stronger coherence with more recent documents such as between the **RBMP** (2022-2027) and **DSF** (2018-2024). Another point of consideration is institution internal cycle such as water agencies which have 5 years strategies with specific strategic objectives that are not aligned in time with **RBMP** cycles what could create incoherence in the implementation mechanism and decision-making related to the **RBMP** program of measures.

Task 3.3: Energy and fishery policy coherence with MSFD, MSPD and WFD

Substance:

The interviews carried highlighted two contradictory facts on the coherence between sectoral policies and marine related planning objectives. On the one hand, the EMFAF and energy farm implementation must be coherent with the **DSF**. On the other hand, there are few relations between all those policies when they are designed, which results in contradictory objectives (economic development prevails for sectoral policies such as employment preservation for fisheries and sectoral development for offshore wind policies). For example, only 1 of the 14 objectives of EMFAF is related to biodiversity protection. Economic development represents ½ of the DSF objectives, the other half being dedicated to biodiversity protection.

As an example potential contradiction and uncoherent effect, the **DSF** has recently gone through a wide debate in France (November 2023-April 2024). This debate aims at gathering feedback on the ground to draft the future **DSF** cycle documents. For this debate, “historic” component of the **DSF** (environment and MSP) only presented half of the interventions (webinars, speaking etc.), the other half being dedicated to the offshore energy topic, lowering the environmental aspect of the DSF debate and underlying the current restructuration of priorities at sea.

The emphasis on the offshore wind energy topic lowers the space given to fisheries in the debate with potential lesser inclusion of fisheries matters in the future **DSF**.

The policies programs of measures also embody the policies priorities. Since 2021, it has been possible for the Regions managing the EMFAF funding to have a “biodiversity” or a “fight against

plastic pollution” objective. This new objective that did not exist before shows an improvement in coherence between sectoral policies and the marine-related policy objectives.

Spatial and temporal scale:

DSF: 2018-2024

RBMP: 2022-2027

EMFAF: 2021-2027

Offshore wind energy: multi-year plan 2009-2028

There is no alignment at all between planning document implementation period. It means that it might create some discrepancy in the realisation of potential contradictory objectives in the period of time when one document has changed before another.

Related to the geographical scope of each policy (see Figure 8), on key challenge lies in the land-sea interface (0.3nm) where many activities, actors, and planning documents overlay with sometimes unaligned objectives (economic development / biodiversity protection).

Figure 8 Planning documents in the land-sea interface

Sectoral policies are articulated with marine-related planning on the same geographical areas, therefore it makes sense that fisheries and offshore wind energy are part of the MSPD.

However, one point of consideration is the offshore wind energy farm construction. Most of the planned ones in the next years are more powerful and will be beyond 12nm. Thus, environmental considerations when granting authorisations are lower.

3. Are the EGD objectives mainstreamed¹ into the policy?

To make reading easier for the authors of the CrossGov 3.2 and 3.3 reports, I separated for this section, the analysis related to 3.2 and 3.3.

Task 3.2: (this section includes DSF, SDAGE, SRADET/SMVM)

As a synthesis of the analysis carried in the two past sections several elements must be underlined related to the EGD:

- First, the timeline is different from the planning document. Only the [RBMP 2022-2027](#) was drafted after the EGD publication in 2020. Thus, it can be understood that the other planning document do not mention explicitly the EGD or its objectives. (As a parenthesis, only one planning document was found mentioning the EGD, the Strategy for the Sea of the Alps-Maritime department published in 2022).
- [DSF](#) and [RBMP](#) objectives support different EGD objectives. Climate change mitigation is for example the overarching objective of the [Rhone-Mediterranean RBMP](#), streamlining all the other objectives. Biodiversity measures in the [DSF](#), the [RBMP](#) as well as the Birds and Habitats Directives and French nature restoration law support, of course, biodiversity protection through both protection and restoration measures. Biodiversity protection involves

¹ Mainstreaming is understood as the integration of key policy and societal goals and considerations across policies from different sectors. In CrossGov, the focus is primarily on the mainstreaming of the EGD marine relevant objectives for biodiversity, climate change and pollution.

all the actors implementing the DSF including the DIRM, DREAL, OFB etc. Finally, the topic of pollution is the responsibility of the RBMP and the Water Agency Rhône-Mediterranean-Corse even at sea (only competencies of the Water Agency going beyond 1nm), it encompasses the struggle against inland pollution (agriculture) as well as plastic pollution.

- Considering DSF and RBMP as two complementary planning document aiming at achieving the same goal (good environmental status) both documents are relatively coherent and partly mainstreaming the EGD Objectives (improvements can be targeted).
- The SRADDET (land planning document) should improve its coherence with the EGD as it is still strongly focus on traditional economic development with few considerations of EGD objectives

Task 3.3: Energy and fishery policy coherence with MSFD, MSPD and WFD

Sectoral policies are key to the EGD implementation. Indeed, cumulative pressure is the source of the ocean challenges including biodiversity loss, pollution, and carbon emissions. Targeting these sectoral policies is essential to preserve the ocean.

- Zero Pollution: Even though the DSF describes sectors as the main target for pollution reduction (maritime transport, energy production nuisance, pollution from fisheries), sectoral policies studied (energy and fisheries as well as sporadically maritime transport) have not integrated EGD objectives on zero pollution. Some activities are carried by the French Biodiversity Office (OFB) along with fishers to track fishnet loss and microplastics at sea through an app. Awareness campaigns are dedicated to the fishers, and tourism sector to reduce plastic pollution, but with no mandatory component. Occitanie region (part of the DSF) has started to work through EMFAF on plastic pollution with fishermen in 2023 what might show a paradigm shift in fisheries management.
- Biodiversity: Biodiversity loss is one of the key challenges of offshore wind development. An assessment guide has been created by the DREAL and put at disposal to private sector for them to properly integrate the challenges and assess their impact on biodiversity. A Green Fund will be open with taxes collected from the offshore wind farms built to support research on biodiversity protection. Regarding EMFAF, only 1/14 of the specific objectives is on biodiversity protection and it is a completely new objective (2022) which aims mostly at supporting MPA protection and dont regulate fisheries on potentially destructive techniques.
- Climate change: the objective of the Law on accelerating the production of renewable energies (March 2023) aims at constructing 50 offshore wind farms to achieve carbon neutrality in 2050. Among them only 4 will be in the Mediterranean Sea. EMFAF briefly makes a mention on climate change in its objectives (support changes of for less-consuming motors) but does not consider it as a guiding principle.

As most of the objectives and actions in sectoral policies are dedicated to economic growth and preserving traditional jobs, EGD is not directly mentioned or mainstreamed by sectoral policies.

Box 3: list of policy instruments available for marine-related policies in the French Mediterranean Sea

The list following list of policy instruments is non-exhaustive but covers the main issues related to the marine environment in the French Mediterranean Sea

Sea-related planning and instruments:

- Legal instruments and regulations:
 - Regional planning document (RBMP, DSF, SRADDET)
 - Local management plans: MPA management plans, STERE (Territorial ecological restoration schemes), (mooring, anchoring etc.), SAGE, contrats de baie (Bay contract)
 - Impact assessment for main planning documents (DSF, RBMP, SRADDET/PADDUC)
- Economic instruments
 - Program of measure of planning documents
 - Projects funding through Water Agency RMC and OFB for research and nature restoration and protection

Sectoral policies planning and management:

- Legal instruments:
 - Fisheries landing obligations, capture control,
 - Permit delivery
 - Geographical and temporal bans
 - Authorization for offshore wind farms
 - The ERC Sequence
- Economic instruments:
 - Support to the fishing industry through EMFAF
 - Funding for research related to offshore wind
 - Future taxes on the offshore wind energy farms

The **ERC sequence** (avoid-reduce-compensation) is a mandatory procedure each construction project at sea must follow to ask for an authorization to build at sea.. It aims to reduce environmental damages and reconciling economic development and environmental issues, by providing a guideline for integrating the environment into planning documents and regional development projects. When a project at sea is instructed, first, the company must try to avoid damaging the environment, if not, to reduce its impact and if none of the two options before it is possible, to compensate by investing in environmental-friendly projects. It is a mix of legal instruments (mandatory), economic instrument (taxes and compensation), compliance procedure (reporting) and information (environmental assessment).

Coherence attribute nr. 2: Policy Instruments

- All mechanisms that are put in place by the policy to achieve its objectives.
 - Set of techniques that governments use, aiming at influencing the behaviour of organisations or individuals in support of public objectives
 - Typologies of policy instruments have been created²

For policies to be coherent:
 - Alignment of policy instruments is considered beneficial for policy coherence.

1. Would / has putting the policy instruments into practice lead / led to results that are in accordance with 1) the policy's own objectives, 2) other policies' objectives, 3) the EGD (CrossGov specific) objectives

² Examples of typologies: Economy (taxes, charges, fees, fines, penalties, liability and compensation schemes, subsidies and incentives, deposit-refund systems, and tradable permit schemes); Information (state-of-the-environment reporting, impact assessments, labelling schemes, technical standards, education campaigns); Legal (licenses, permits, prescriptions, prohibitions, bans); Compliance procedures (including monitoring and reporting schemes); Enforcement procedures (litigation and access to justice).

To make reading easier for the authors of the CrossGov 3.2 and 3.3 reports, I separated for this section the analysis related to 3.2 and 3.3.

Task 3.2: (this section includes DSF, SDAGE, SRADET/SMVM, local plannings)

The main tools to implement the WFD, MSFD and MSPD are their planning documents and related programs of measures.

The DSF (MSFD/MSPD) and its objectives are implemented through 81 operational measures. The RBMP (WFD) has 276 actions in total related to the marine environment (186 on transitional waters and 90 on coastal waters including 49 on mooring, 24 on bathing areas, 25 on reducing pollution by hazardous substances).

The DSF environmental impact assessment indicates that 80% of pollution in the Mediterranean Sea comes from land. This observation puts into perspective the scope of the DSF's efforts to limit coastal pollution and highlights that significant progress in integrated land-sea management is still expected to achieve good environmental status of marine waters. This evaluation requires that efforts be made in the watershed (RBMP) otherwise the DSF cannot achieve its objectives.

In order to improve the state of the sea and reach their own objectives, both the Interregional Directorate of the Sea and Water Agency RMC provide support through funding collectivities and municipalities into drafting new sea enhancement plans to control activities polluting the sea and restoring ecosystems. Such management plans, called STERE, are still under development and 4 of them are supported in the Mediterranean coast (Adge, Marseille, Nice-Côte d'Azur and Saint-Tropez).

To support the implementation of these measures, fundings have a strong role. In 2023, four complementary calls for funding have been published by the DIRM on ecological restoration strategy, impact of diving activity on frequented sites, dredging and land management of dredged sediments, pooling and valorisation and characterisation and functioning of soft substrate habitats.

The French Biodiversity office (OFB) and the Water Agency (AERMC) have many calls open to support biodiversity protection and ecosystem restoration including the protection of Posidonia seagrass meadows, as well as support MPA management (mooring and anchoring regulations).

However, such funding has a very local effect but does not encompass a global solution to reach GES on "biodiversity", climate change", "zero pollution". To achieve such goals, a global strategy and related measures must be set up to counter the effect of cumulative impacts (including sectoral policies).

ERC methodology (avoid-reduce-compensate) (described in box 3) could be effective, but it requires the right scientific knowledge to understand the state of the sea before the project and forecast potential effects on the ecosystems.

Finally, at a local level, the multiplication of policy objectives can lead to discrepancies where local actor does not know how to comply with and balance all the policies requirement and give up on building a management plan that could encompass all the policy requirements.

Thus, MSFD and MSPD policy instruments can support the three EGD objectives only if they are carried out efficiently and that the projects do not benefit from exemptions and that they include sectors in their regulations (especially marine transport).

9 superposition of plans on a small municipality (modified from Blouet 2024)

Task 3.3: Energy and fishery policy coherence with MSFD, MSPD and WFD

Policy instruments for sectoral policies are more targeted than the ones for the implementation of marine-related policies.

The coherence with biodiversity and climate change goals of sectoral policies are mostly driven by a combination of regulations and fundings (stick and carrots).

Fishery objectives are driven through funding (EMFAF) and regulation (temporal and geographic bans, landing obligations, licenses, maximum sustainable yield etc.).

Marine renewable energies development depends on authorizations, environmental impact assessments and the state of scientific knowledge.

Regarding their own objectives, fisheries and energy policies have a rather economic orientation (employment, infrastructure construction, etc.). At the regional scale, on fisheries there are few complaints regarding the financial mechanisms (e.g. EMFAF distribution) and only some about the regulations (mostly on bans in MPA not being respected by foreign ships). However, voices have been raised regarding the implementation of wind farms in the sea where fishing was occurring (public meeting in 2023). This is due to competitive interest in the same areas (offshore wind farms are constructed where there is wind and where there is upwelling attracting most of the fishes). To reduce conflict of use, Emmanuel Macron, French President, declared in a public statement that 30% of the taxes collected from the new offshore wind farm would be dedicated to supporting fisheries.

Offshore wind:

Regarding other policies, some incoherences and bottlenecks exist.

The difference in objective (economic and sectoral development against good environmental status) can lead to contradictory effects of the offshore wind program of measure. The multi-annual plan for energy development in France drastically increased the number of offshore wind farms to be developed by without taking into account the time to collect scientific data to avoid harmful authorization. Two calls were launched in 2023 (20 million) and 2024 (6 million) to improve the knowledge on pre-selected areas for offshore wind development. However, without a strict frame, authorizations might be granted without sufficient knowledge.

Fisheries

During the EMFAF call for project drafting, the Interregional Directorate and the Region (managing EMFAF) work closely to ensure coherence between EMFAF-supported projects and MaS. The 2021-2027 national fisheries operational program is aligned with the priorities of the Mediterranean MaS action plan, focusing on environmental sustainability, innovation development, the promotion of sustainable aquaculture, and the marketing and processing of fishery and aquaculture products. A clear mention is made to Mediterranean MaS and the science-policy interface: "Priority will be given to projects that include a dimension of improving knowledge of the impact of climate change on stocks of interest to fisheries. Projects will be able to draw on data sets collected within other frameworks, in particular data collected under the MaS (EMFAF specific objective OS1.4) or the MSFD¹⁸".

However, despite these close links on paper, the National EMFAF strategy primarily focuses its biodiversity funds efforts on data collection and raising awareness in MPAs. EMFAF is not yet sufficiently oriented to be used as a concrete incentive for fishing that is closely linked to the sustainable use of resources. The main mechanisms for enforcing compliance with CFP stock sustainability objectives and MSFD indicators remain regulatory and coercive, through temporary bans and landing obligations.

There are also conflicts of priorities between biodiversity protection tools and fisheries priority and fundings. Local management plans such as MPA management plans, *Bay contracts* (a comprehensive, concerted approach to restoring the quality of water and aquatic environments, involving all stakeholders in a 5-year action programme), *STERE* (Territorial ecological restoration schemes) are often criticised by the sectors as such decision-making would have a negative economic impact (fisheries restriction, marine navigation speed limit, anchoring forbidden, mooring mandatory, etc.). Conversely, harmful subsidies such as a financial support of 40 cts per litre of fuel through EMFAF have a negative impact on biodiversity protection and climate change.

Regarding the three Green Deal objectives, policy instruments have contradictory effects. On climate change, building offshore wind energy farms can have long-term positive impacts but it is inconsistent with fisheries harmful subsidies. On biodiversity protection, almost no funding is dedicated to the topic in both sectors. Finally, on 0 pollution, offshore wind energy farms and harmful subsidies both have negative effects.

2. To what extent are spatial and temporal scales aligned between instruments of the different policies?

There is no specific spatial and temporal alignment between policy instruments. Except considering MPA management plans and some *contrat de baie* /*STERE* where there is a strong concentration of instruments at the same time and place.

Spatial scale

A question that arises about spatial scale is the potential overlap between policy instruments. For example, there is an overlap of funding between the Water Agency (AERMC) and the French Biodiversity Office (OFB) because both institutions are competent up to 1mn. An unofficial difference has been set up: the Water Agency (AERMC) works with an efficiency and operational perspective “collecting data on what I can change” while the French Biodiversity Office (OFB) collects and produces a lot of “knowledge for knowledge’s sake” (interview).

Temporal scale

One contradiction has been found between the multi-annual plan on energy and the MSFD program of measure.

This *DSF* is also the strategic environmental assessment (SEA) for a given maritime façade. However, given the fast acceleration of offshore wind energy development, the *DSF* drafted in 2017 has shown limitation as at the time of its adoption, the French Energy Plan Decree was still in preparation, resulting in the targets not being specified in the strategic objectives. Given that the regulatory obligations for strategic environmental assessment are described in the *DSF*, they did not incorporate the zoning required to meet the objectives of the French Energy Plan relating to marine renewable energy with sufficient detail. SEAs have therefore been unable to completely integrate the impacts of the offshore wind energy development from the French Energy programming, nor the cumulative impacts with those of other activities.

3. Do the instruments support the cross-fertilisation of information and knowledge across policies with similar instruments?

As most of the institution involved in the marine environment work together, the projects funded and the guiding document developed (e.g. guidance on how to apply the ERC at sea) support the other policy instruments. For example, most of the actors provide funding to protect *Posidonia* or to support MPAs. To go beyond in this direction, in 2023, the *DIRM* and *Water Agency RMC* launched their first common funding call on biodiversity protection.

As another example in how instruments (financial and legal) can support each other, the DIRM and OFB work together on fisheries. The MSFD asks that there be an evaluation of the entire activity and not boat by boat. The French Biodiversity Office (OFB) helps the Interregional Directorate for the Mediterranean Sea (DIRM) via EMFAF funding to carry out this analysis, particularly on the impacts on habitats and their sensitivity to fishing, but also to see if there are any good practices. This reporting can support EMFAF as well.

Finally, there is a cross-fertilisation of policies between MSFD and WFD. The DSF and RBMP programs of measures support each other for historical reasons. The DSF (2014) has been set up to complete what was not already covered by the RBMP (2008). Thus, MSFD indicators D5 and D8 on eutrophication and pollution have remained a competency of the Water Agency and of the RBMP. Data collected then help fertilize the assessment reports of the DSF and MSFD. Cross-fertilization of knowledge is now supported by a new platform created in October 2024 that compiles data for both directives (MSFD and WFD).

Finally, the DSF program of measures support also the EMFAF and marine renewable energy strategy objectives.

4. Do policies have shared implementation mechanisms (shared licensing, common indicators, shared monitoring frameworks)?

Common indicators

MSFD indicators D5 and D8 on eutrophication and pollution have remained a competency of the Water Agency and of the RBMP.

However, some other indicators are still not aligned (e.g. between MSFD and WFD on the good status of Posidonia for example) which makes it difficult to implement projects at a local level because indicators are sometimes good for one directive but not for the other with the same collected data (interview).

Common indicators are under development since 2014 (source: webinar IFREMER) but local actors have underlined the inconsistency of these indicators that can create irrelevant decision-making (e.g. in 2018, sewage waters from the new sewage station of the city of Montpellier were considered as too polluted to be discharged into rivers but good enough to be discharged directly into the sea).

Common monitoring systems

There is a share in the monitoring system such as the WFD monitoring which are used for MSFD including data on physiochemistry, phytoplankton, green tides, coastal benthic habitats, etc.

Most of the monitoring schemes in the second cycle of the "Benthic Habitats" monitoring program have an established link with other European directives, mainly the Water Framework Directive (WFD - 2000/60/EC) and the Habitats and Fauna Directive (HFD - 92/43/EEC).

Cross-fertilization of knowledge is now supported by a new platform created in October 2024 that compiles data for both directives (MSFD and WFD).

Data such as boat counting for fisheries are shared between the Interregional Directorate for the Mediterranean Sea (DIRM) and the Region as it fuels both the DSF and the EMFAF databases.

5. Do the policy instruments provide mechanisms to deal with conflicting objectives, incentives, etc.?

Depending on the level of implementation of the policy instrument, some mechanisms exist to reduce conflicts but in reality, very few are implemented.

Many policy instruments exist to reduce conflicts between MSFD and WFD. It includes:

- A mandatory coherence between both program of measure (meetings during preparatory phases)
- Yearly common meeting (2 per year)
- Cross-references between relevant measures of each programs of measure
- Cross-references in mid-term and end-of-term review of actions
- Common call for projects

- Invitation of DSF representative during local meetings to follow-up on implementation of the RBMP

To reduce conflicts between MSFD and fisheries:

- Common meetings (2 per year)
- Meetings during preparatory phases
- Common work on some objectives and indicators (EMFAF fund objective on biodiversity supports MSFD)

There are still conflicting measures as objectives are not similar (economic development against good environmental status). Taking the example of harmful subsidies, no mechanism has been implemented even if it is contradictory with MSFD and the EGD objectives because it comes from a political and societal demand.

Two main mechanisms exist to reduce conflicting objectives for offshore wind energy:

- The environmental impact assessment, mandatory for planning documents and to get autorisation for an economic activity
- The ERC procedure which imposes on every company with an infrastructure project to either avoid the damaging effect on the environment or to “pay” for a compensation. Unfortunately, most of the procedures end up with a “compensate” status which is often difficult to evaluate without the right scientific knowledge, as it is almost impossible to put a price on an ecosystem.

Institutional mechanisms exist to check the coherence between projects supported and the planning document objectives (e.g. (Regional Department for the Environment, Planning and Housing) checking if projects supported by Water Agency (AERMC) comply with the MSFD)

After evaluating the two Coherence Attributes (policy objectives and instruments), you are now requested to explore the three sets of Explanatory Variables that help explain why a certain level of policy coherence is observed. If you found explanations that do not fit into any of these three categories, please document the information in the additional box provided at the end.

Explanatory variable nr. 1: Governmental organizational structures	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structures (within/across local, regional and national authorities, EU and international organisations) that set the framework within which policies are formulated and implemented. - These structures include the involved and responsible governmental organisations, their roles and responsibilities, their ability to address broader issues than their own “silo” issues, as well as their coordination mechanisms 	<p>It plays a role in the level of coherence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organizational behaviour and collaboration to overcome working in silos (e.g. coordination and collaboration within and across organisations³) - Clear mandates aimed at overcoming barriers - Clear responsibilities to work towards EGD objectives, and clear means to do so
<p><i>1. Are the mandates and roles of governmental organisations governing a policy issue clearly defined (overlaps or redundancies)? How does this affect their involvement in policy formulation and implementation, and their collaboration with other organisations?</i></p>	
<p>To make reading easier for the authors of the CrossGov 3.2 and 3.3 reports, I separated for this section, the analysis related to 3.2 and 3.3.</p> <p>As shown in the Box 1, many actors are involved in the marine-related planning, and a 96-pages booklet has been published by the Interregional Directorate for the Mediterranean Sea (DIRM) in 2016 to explain the repartition of competencies of “The State on the coast and in the Mediterranean Sea”.</p> <p>This section won’t cover all the institution’s competencies but approach what works and what does not in a non-exhaustive way.</p>	
<p>Task 3.2: (this section includes DSF, SDAGE, SRADET/SMVM)</p> <p>In France, MSFD and MSPD are well aligned thanks to the DSF which is a French specificity. To align biodiversity conservation (MSFD) and economic development (MSPD), France draws every 6 years a National Strategy on the Sea and Coastline. This strategy is then declined for each French sea under one planning document called the “Document Stratégique de façade”. This document is the operational implementation of both the MSFD and MSPD. Through “vocational maps”, this planning document explains for each local geographic divisions what are the environmental and the economic challenges. The objective is to better align the environmental and economic policies (including fisheries).</p> <p>Most of those interviewees stressed that the division of responsibilities between the DSF (MSFD and MSPD) and the RBMP is working effectively, and that the coordination allows them to implement most of the actions from the program of measures.</p> <p>Some of the responsibilities are difficult to understand such as the Water Agency (AERMC) who has competencies on inland and coastal waters (1nm) except for marine pollution where it has competencies on the whole public maritime domain.</p> <p>Overlap in the budget of biodiversity measures:</p> <p>The Water Agency (AERMC)’s “biodiversity” budget is shared with the OFB’s Mediterranean Branch, which, according to the division of powers, is responsible for protecting biodiversity. However, if one of these two institutions uses the budget to restore Posidonia meadows, for example, which is within its remit, then the other institution (Water AgencyRMC) should not use the budget to restore Posidonia meadows. As these two institutions work on the same topic (as do the mooring strategies), there is a strong overlap which has been highlighted as a problem on several occasions (interviews). This situation is specific to the Mediterranean façade where the Water Agency RMC is strongly</p>	

³ Formalised processes such as the creation of supra- or lead institutions, inter-ministerial committees, joint task forces and decision-making bodies; or ad-hoc and informal coordination mechanisms.

involved in the marine environment and this situation does not exist in another façade. The need for more frequent meetings has been underlined (interviews) to align the roles and responsibilities of each institution, especially on habitat protection and restoration in the coastal area (1nm).

Gaps in Corsica's region

Another strong example is the one of Corsica who has several organisations of competency difficulties (source interview). Corsica is included in the **AERMC** perimeter and in the **DSF-Mediterranean**. However, the island has a unique administrative status and different stakes and challenges than the French inland coastline (less industrialization). Thus, Corsican's feeling is that they are:

- underrepresented (only 1 representative in the Façade Maritime Council while there are more than 15 of the PACA and Occitanie regions),
- not included (DSF discussion at the national level and with inland stakes, decisions taken by the Maritime Prefecture (PREMAR) in Corsica's waters without informing the Corsican's assembly)
- rarely considered (Water Agency (AERMC) covers Corsica in their strategic discussions while Corsica has different water issues than the Rhône basin).

Corsica wants the Mediterranean coast and the AERMC to refocus planning and strategy documents on the challenges facing their territory (interview).

Overlaps in the local level implementation

As underlined before, the local scale is at the forefront of policy implementation. However, in a very small area, many of the policies must be implemented (see section before). This multiplies the number of stakeholders with whom these local stakeholders must interact to draw up and implement their **Sea-enhancement Plans (SCOT-SMVM)**, a strategic plan drafted and implemented by a municipality to develop sea-related activities) or MPA management document. The information is scattered, and it makes the preparation of administrative and funding dossiers very complex, with authorisations to be requested from the Departmental Directorate for the Sea (DDTM, departmental branch of the **DIRM** and **DREAL**) environmental dossiers from the DREAL, and funding from the OFB and the **AERMC** depending on the theme (protection of biodiversity, creation of STEREs). This leads to many local actors not drafting nor implementing sea-related plans to avoid facing this administrative difficulties.

Furthermore, there seems to be a barrier between the local institutions that implement the policies and the regional institutions that draw up the obligations to be met. Dialogue has not been established, which is regretted by the local players.

Task 3.3: Energy and fishery policy coherence with MSFD, MSPD and WFD

Sectoral policies are implemented by different institutions than the marine-related ones. It is mostly the Regional Administration which are in charge of the fisheries management (in collaboration with the DIRM for some actions of the DSF) and the Ministry of ecological transition what can support in the future a better coherence between the biodiversity and fisheries policies.

On offshore wind energy, competency repartition is blurry. The regulation and planning of offshore wind energy in France are centralised at the national level, under the supervision of the Ministry of the Ecological Transition and Solidarity. Different institutions are involved in the granting of authorisations. If the windfarm is located on the public maritime domain, the concession for use of the public maritime domain is issued by the Departmental Prefect. In the EEZ, the authorization is granted by the Maritime Prefect. Actors are not exactly the same as for marine policies and do not have same objectives;

However, there are more and more actors involved in these policies that could create redundancies on the mid-term. Starting in 2025, the Water Agency RMC will have competencies to manage the offshore wind energy taxes to improve biodiversity protection and research on the marine environment up to 200 nautic. Their competencies were only covering 12 nautical miles until now and further, only the interregional Directorate of the Sea was competent. This new fact blurs the competencies repartition at sea.

2. Which intra- and inter-organizational (formal and informal) coordination mechanisms are in place and how do they support coordination across policies?

This section contains similar elements to question 1 of variable 3 .

Formal coordination mechanisms

- Consultations are organised by Water Agency RMC and DIRM/DREAL when their related programs of measures are designed. There are also discussions between Region and DIRM on the EMFAF mechanism design to avoid incoherence with the DSF.
- Once per year, technical 1-day meeting (e.g. seagrass, mooring) is organised between DIRM/ DREAL/OFB/AERMC
- DIRM and OFB are invited to Basin Committees (but recognised they don't attend because of a lack of time).
- DIRM, DREAL and Environmental Agency are located in the same office what facilitates the coordination of work

Experts inside the institutions

- The presence of actors specialised in the marine environment in the AERMC facilitates the link between fresh and sea waters
- One inconsistency that has been found is that the DREAL's environmental specialists are the ones who will be dealing with offshore wind farm projects, without involving the DREAL's marine and biodiversity department.

3. Are spatial and temporal scales of governmental organisations well aligned and also fit-for-purpose for the relevant policy issues areas?

The question is either not clear enough or has redundancies with question 1.

Spatial scale:

As previously mentioned, the spatial scale is fully covered in the Mediterranean area as the MSFD covers areas that were not covered by the WFD.

One point of attention is the repartition of competencies between 12 and 200 nautical miles (where the Maritime Prefect has the competency to resources exploitations. Decision-making is less debated (few involvement of regional stakeholders and no mandatory consultation of the environmental agency) . Environmental impact studies may be less thorough since the Maritime Prefect can grant derogations and exemptions (RED III). This geographical repartition of competencies have a strong impact on offshore wind energy farms authorizations and localization.

Temporal scale

- There are not enough Maritime Façade Council meetings (only 2 per year) to provide relevant information to all the policy issues related to the Mediterranean.
- With a dozen or so institutional players, a dozen or so plans to implement and different timeframes for these plans, temporal scale might not be adequate (e.g. a measure from WFD which is relevant for MSFD is not included in the program of measures because the environmental impact assessment of the DSF takes place after the elaboration of the RBMP and 6 years must be waited to implement this measures, unalignment between DSF program of measure and multi-yearly energy plan etc.).
- Internally, conflict exists. For example, the Water Agency RMC, for example, has a program of measures from 2022 to 2027 but an internal programme from 2024 to 2029 what can create incoherence.

To answer the question, the repartition of competencies within the maritime public domain might work well, but some improvement must be made between 12-200nm as well as in the timeframes.

4. How does resource allocation within governmental organisations affect their ability to formulate and implement policies, and to collaborate with other organisations

Funding

The Water Agency (AERMC) is a state operator, what means they are allowed to receive funding what States services (DREAL, DIRM) cannot do. Thus the funding for the DSF is first managed by the Water Agency (AERMC) and then shared among all partners. This can lead to a wrong interpretation of the role of the Water agency.

As underlined in question 1, this repartition of budget can create an overlap between institutions competencies (biodiversity).

10 Funding evolution of the DSF POM 2016-2018

Human resources

Most of the State Services are overloaded with work on what can create difficulties to collaborate and ensure coherence between policies (DREAL, DIRM and DDTM).

Civil servant specialisation (science) can make the instruction of policies difficult (scientific people working in the administration with few visions on the socio-economic issues).

At a local level, human resources can be a source of incoherence. The one working on marine environment is not always specialised in marine environment (ex: Land-sea Natura 2000 managed by terrestrial people and not marine people who give up working on the marine part of their Natura 2000 site).

More and more is asked at the local level (creation of STERE, contrat de baie etc) but their sources in the public administrations do not follow, especially when it is to hire people (elimination of operating funding).

Municipalities are also being asked to give their opinion on the siting of offshore wind farms, as they will be affected by the royalty taxes, but without being trained in the issues at stake.

The role of NGOs once again appears to be essential in relaying the lack of resources in the public administration (link with fisheries).

5. How do political processes and power dynamics within and between governmental organisations affect their influence on policy formulation and implementation?

This section must be completed as few information was found so far.

- There is a strong state control even on the Mediterranean area challenges:
 - The 1st DSF POM was centralised and elaborated by the Secretariat of the Sea without taking into account regional DIRM
 - The State has imposed the DSF 2024 debate to include a strong part on offshore wind (see section below) while it is not the core of the Mediterranean challenges
- There is a hierarchy of institutions between state services and regional operators which can lead to poor consideration of the actors of each (Water-Agency RMC marginalised)

Explanatory variable nr. 3: Stakeholder involvement⁴

- Manner in which stakeholders influence policy framing, design and implementation through participatory processes and other avenues such as information campaigns and lobbying, and how this affects coherence across policies.

It plays a role in the level of coherence:

- Inclusive, participatory mechanisms that enable active exchange across a broad set of actors and interests, are more likely to have a stronger contribution to coherence than processes involving few interests that may be typical “clients” for one sector only
- Involvement of different stakeholders in policy making and implementation processes enables integration of different information, knowledge, values and ideas and fosters agreement and buy in across different interest groups

1. To what extent does stakeholder involvement affect policy choices during design and implementation, and how does this impact coherence across policies?

As previously explained, most of the sectoral policies are designed at the European level (Common Fisheries Policy), or the national level (EMFAF, marine renewable energy laws) which leaves very few spaces to stakeholder involvement. Even for regional institutions or regional branches (DIRM, DREAL, AERMC, OFB), who then implement those policies and strategies.

Design:

11 Elaboration of the DSF

- DSF (MSFD/MSPD): the DSF is designed at the national scale, but suggestions can be made under two processes:
 - The Façade Maritime Council (CMF): inherited from the Grenelle de Environment (2007) this consultative body gathers more than 50 actors from 7 categories of stakeholders (State and public bodies, local representatives, private sectors, syndicates, NGOs, experts, specialised institutions and universities). In the façade maritime Council, many of the key stakeholders are involved allowing a cross-sectoral and cross-policy co-creation and discussion (WFD, MSFD, MSPD). During the DSF drafting phase, they propose major issues and challenges to deal with to the Maritime Prefecture (PREMAR).
 - The DSF debates for the new cycle (2024-2029) gathered from March 2023 to April 2024 people through more than 100 webinars and 200 public debates in local places through the whole littoral territory in France. During this debate, a platform was open to collect “cahiers d’acteurs” (stakeholders' booklets) on what they think is important. Everyone could contribute including NGOs (e.g. WWF, FNE, Surfrider, LFO

⁴ This explanatory variable of Stakeholder Involvement explicitly focuses on how stakeholders shape policy alternatives both during the formulation and design of policies as well as their implementation. The explanatory variable of SPSI sheds light on how stakeholders influence the production and transfer of knowledge.

contributed to a cross-NGO booklet on the MSP and the offshore wind farm implantation in the future DSF maps) (more information on the DSF debate in Annex 20).

- Another notable good practice was the “Assise du littoral”, a year of public debate in Corsica in 2011 to build a regional strategy for the sea that was then implemented in the [Corsica's sustainable development plan](#) (PADDUC). This process was more inclusive and gave more influence to the local stakeholders than the one organised in the mainland France.
- There is also institutional stakeholders' involvement within state institutions such as consultation organised by the Water Agency (AERMC) and DIRM/DREAL when their related POM is designed. There are also discussions between Region and DIRM on the EMFAF mechanism design to avoid incoherence with the DSF.
- Not sure the lobbying campaigns are very relevant at the “regional scale” as most of the decisions are taken at the national scale where clearly fisheries and Electricity Transmission Network (French company called RTE) have a strong influence (few companies working on marine renewable energy in France)
- Unlike for [RBMP](#) and [DSF](#) which have joint consultation bodies, land-planning document ([SRADDET](#)) was designed without consulting the [Water Agency \(AERMC\)](#) and the [Interregional Directorate for the Mediterranean Sea \(DIRM\)](#). Thus, even if both documents' objectives and implementation must legally comply with SDAGE and DSF objectives some discrepancy can be found leading to incoherence.

Implementation:

- In the implementation at the regional level, the process is rather top-down and private sector is involved through information campaigns to change private sectors habits. The private sector has more influence at the local level (ex: campaigning anti-moorings).
- The importance of involving the civil society (NGOs such as FNE and WWF among others) has been underlined (interviews) as NGOs create a link with local stakeholders who mistrust the state representatives. Such NGO involvement can support coherence between policies as they provide expertise when a lack is identified. For example, France Nature Environnement (FNE) took position when Montpellier renewed its wastewater treatment plan because, to be in accordance with WFD indicators, the municipality decided to release their sewage waters in the sea where it did not impact indicators because there was no monitoring stations at the discharge location (2018).
- Finally, there is a significant barrier when arriving at the local level (drafting of MPA management plans, [SMVM](#), [contrats de baie](#) etc.), because local actors are not really involved in the policy design, making it difficult for them to implement those planning documents when they received the [SDAGE](#), [DSF](#) and related program of measures as well as Habitats and Birds Directives which make a total of more than 5000 pages of requirements to read and implement in the Mediterranean region (source: workshop organised in April 2023).

2. In how far formal and informal stakeholder involvement mechanisms at different stages of the policy cycle are aligned across policies?

The regular and formal meeting organised including the Façade Maritime Council twice per year, the annual technical meetings involving state services (DIRM, DREAL, AERMC, OFB) allow aligning some of the policy objectives, measures indicators and funded projects. It allows to ensure greater coherence throughout the policy implementation cycle. For example, the contributions of experts and NGOs contribute to improving the scientific quality of the indicators and monitoring system (influence of FNE on the current monitoring system of the DSF).

No information was found on formal mechanisms to involve/align sectors with [RBMP](#) and [DSF](#) except during the consultation process to define the MSP priorities. Public meetings have been organised in 2023 to present the offshore energy projects to fishermen to collect their needs but there was no information on how and if their will were taken into account.

3. In how far participatory processes do (e.g. stakeholder platforms) in the process support the involvement of stakeholders across different policy areas/sectors?

The different participatory processes presented in the two previous questions allow involving a wide variety of stakeholders.

- As a major example, the Façade maritime council is composed of more than 50 representatives from 6 different groups including the private sectors, syndicates and NGOs as follow:
 - College of representatives of the State and public bodies (17 members)
 - College of local authorities and their groupings (20 members)
 - College of professional and business representatives (17 members)
 - College of company employee representatives (3 members)
 - College of associations for the protection of the coastal or marine environment or users of the sea and coastline (18 members)
 - Qualified experts (5 members)

Among them, sectors are represented such as Sylvain Pioch (interview) Professors at University level in geography and marine renewable energies, 5 representatives of fisheries industries, 1 of the renewable marine energy sectors. Regarding the weight of the industries, fisheries are overrepresented in terms of member to cover the whole French Mediterranean area.

However, the lack of interest in the debates was highlighted, since the Standing Committee is often composed of the elected representatives who speak of but do not know the subjects.

In the Façade maritime Council, there are three different committees covering: marine renewable energies, MPAs and strong protection, as well as marine jobs. Everyone can make suggestions and have an influence on the decisions taken (interview with NGOs FNE and WWF). However, the Façade Maritime Council is a consultative body and the discussions and suggestions made are adopted at the appreciation of the Maritime Prefecture (PREMAR). There is no transparency in the decision made afterwards.

As previously mentioned, all the participatory processes including the civil society made at the regional level or at the national level (DSF consultation currently ongoing) are only consultative. Most of the decision is taken internally to the institutions.

4. Are the consultation/participatory processes inclusive, fair, and equitable ensuring contributions of all relevant stakeholders or do power imbalances mean that contributions are biased towards certain stakeholders?

As mentioned, in the previous sections, “Sea” is a matter of State thus there is an imbalance in the decisions taken where the national strategy prevails over the regional and local stakes. Even though every actor can participate at one stage or another in the discussion to create/renew marine related planning documents, it does not mean that every contribution is considered at an equal level.

CMF is a place where a participant can be heard as well as public consultation but:

- Final decisions on the DSF are taken at the national level
- Final decisions on the RBMP are taken inside the AERMC
- Final decisions on marine renewable energies are at the hand of the PREMAR (thus the State)
- Region has few handling on the EMFAF management

Thus, the participatory and consultant processes are inclusive (everyone can participate), fair (public debates in more than 200 different places in France in 2023-2024 on the sea) and equitable (possibility for everyone to ask questions and submit a “cahier d’acteur” to propose ideas).

Private sector organisation are more represented when drafting, designing and implementing sectoral policies.

However, at the end of the process, states representative take the decisions and the participatory and consultant processes do not counteract power imbalances.